

PMK1, an improved rainfed lowland rice variety for Tamil Nadu, India

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PMK1 (Co 25/ADT31), a high-yielding, and widely adapted rainfed lowland rice variety, matures in 115-120 d. It has long, compact panicles with golden yellow grains, white rice, and good cooking quality.

The early seedling vigor exhibited by

Performance of PMK1 in research station and adaptive research trials. Tamil Nadu, India, 1980-83.

Year	Yield (t/ha)		Increase (%) over TKM9
	PMK1	TKM9	
1980	3.4	2.8	21.9
1981	3.0	2.2	36.1
1982	3.0	2.5	18.1
1983	2.2	1.9	19.7
Mean ^a	2.9	2.3	23.9
1983 ^b	3.1	2.7	12.1

^aResearch station trials. ^bAdaptive research trials, 20 sites.

PMK1 helps it compete with weeds at the early vegetative phase.

In yield trials for 4 yr in Aug-Dec season, average grain yield were 2.9 t/ha, 23.9% more than TKM9, a high-yielding, semidwarf, rainfed lowland rice (see table). In the Adaptive Research Trials of 1983-84, PMK1 produced an average grain yield of 3.06 t/ha, 12.1% more than TKM9. It is a good straw yielder as well.

PMK1 is 110 cm high, photoperiod insensitive, and lodging resistant. It matures in 120 d. A thousand grains weigh 24 g and cooking quality 15 good.

PMK1 is tolerant of blast and bacterial leaf blight in the field. *☞*

NC492 (IET8970), a promising variety for rainfed lowlands in West Bengal

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NC492, a pureline selection from Boyan (Acc. 30250), was identified at Chinsurah after it survived submergence for 3 d in late Sep 1978, when a record 523.9 mm of rain fell at RRS 15 d after planting. In station trials and adaptive trials at 6 sites from 1979 to 1982, NC492 yielded an average 4.7 t/ha, compared to 3.4 t/ha for Mahsuri.

NC492 was nominated for the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) semideep water trial (Uniform Variety Trial 5 [UVT 5]) and tested at 7 sites during 1982 kharif. It ranked first (3.8 t/ha) in overall mean yield (Table 1).

In tests at 11 sites in 1983, NC492 ranked second, with a marginal yield difference of only 45 kg/ha less than the first ranking variety CN505-5-32-9 (IET8967). In 1984, NC492 yielded an average 2.9 t/ha at 8 sites. It ranked first in the Physiology Screening Trial for waterlogged conditions (AICRIP) conducted with UVT 5 entries in 1982 and 1983 (Table 2).

NC492 is photoperiod sensitive, lowering in late October. It is semitall

Table 1. Performance of NC492 in 1982-83 national trials (UVT 5). West Bengal, India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)				Maximum water depth (cm)	
	NC492		Tillakkachari		1982	1983
	1982	1983	1982	1983		
Pulla	3.2	2.4	1.8	1.6	70	75
Patna	3.2	2.6	2.8	2.0	—	31
Pusa	2.7	1.4	2.1	0.8	70	60
Sindri	1.3	3.7	1.3	2.9	50	36
Bhubaneswar	4.6	—	2.3	—	—	—
Chinsurah	6.2	3.1	4.3	1.6	40	50
Cuttack Rice Research Institute	—	3.6	—	2.7	—	41
Ranital	—	4.6	—	2.4	—	—
Sabour	—	1.0	—	1.1	—	63
Arundhutinagar	5.1	—	4.1	—	—	—
Mean	3.8	2.8	2.6	1.8	—	—

Table 2. Performance of NC492 in 1982-83 Physiology Screening Trials for waterlogged conditions (AICRIP).

Site	Yield (t/ha)					
	NC492		Tillakkachari		Other check	
	1982	1983	1982	1983	1982	1983
Baruipur	4.5	4.5	3.9	3.8	2.9	1.0
Chinsurah	4.9	5.3	3.1	4.7	(Mahsuri) 4.3	(Pankaj) 4.2
Cuttack	3.4	4.7	3.2	3.7	(NC488) 3.1	(NC487) 3.1
Patna	4.2	3.2	4.6	4.0	(Mahsuri) 2.6	(Mahsuri) 2.1
Mean	4.2	4.5	3.7	4.0	(Pankaj) 3.2	(BR34) 2.6

(about 150 cm) with moderate culm stiffness and good seedling vigor. The panicle is about 26 cm long with 160-170

golden color grains.

The variety has a shape index of 3.75, 1,000-grain weight of 32 g, and strong